

Full-Wave-Based Emulation of Forward-Looking Radar Target Imaging in Rough Terrain Environment

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Abstract—Large-scale full-wave modeling of multistatic target imaging in a rough ground environment is described. The emulation methodology employs a parallelized three-dimensional finite-difference time-domain (FDTD) algorithm in characterizing the near-grazing angle electromagnetic scattering from the ground surface and buried and on-surface targets in the form of landmines and unexploded ordnances (UXO); subsequent focusing of the scattered fields into an image is obtained with the time-reversal technique. The emphasis of this study is on investigating the detectability of discrete ground targets in the presence of distributed variable ground clutter as relevant to performance prediction for ultra-wideband forward-looking radar applications.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE detection and identification of landmines and unexploded ordnances (UXO) is a difficult problem that has continuously challenged our military's scientific and technological expertise. Of the various mitigation efforts the U.S. Army has undertaken over the years in response to these threats, sensing with radio waves has garnered the most attention—and also has gradually become the most prominent technique; in this method, a transmitter illuminates a scene with electromagnetic signals and then the reflected—or scattered—signals are recorded and processed to identify the presence and locations of potential targets. As a target's signature is often distorted or obscured by the responses from the environment, the ability to model and simulate the target's electromagnetic interactions with its surroundings is therefore critical in the design of high fidelity detection systems.

Recently, there has been considerable interest in the application of ground-based mobile sensing platforms for standoff detection and identification of in-road and roadside threats. One promising technology developed at the U.S. Army Research Laboratory (ARL) is the low-frequency ultra-wideband synchronous impulse reconstruction (SIRE) radar [1], which is a vehicle-based system operating at the nominal frequency band of 500 MHz–2500 MHz with the forward-looking coverage angle θ_{inc} spanning approximately $5^\circ - 15^\circ$ with respect to the horizon (Fig. 1). In analyzing a low-to-ground system such as the SIRE radar, as the radiowave propagation paths defining the electromagnetic interactions between the radar transceiver and the targets adhere to the ground, existing ground surface scattering models must be supplemented, or extended, to include low-grazing angle effects. The complicated scattering interactions of the targets and the ground,

consequently, are intricate functions of the radar geometry (i.e., signal incidence and observation angles), transmission and reception polarizations, frequency, as well as the electrical and physical properties of the terrain. Accordingly, full-wave electromagnetic simulations are needed—and have been purposefully undertaken—to estimate the performance of the forward-looking radar. In particular, the subject of interest in this work is the scattering behaviors of realistic random ground surfaces in the backscattering directions and their effects on the imaging of both buried and on-surface target classes.

Previous efforts in systematically modeling the operation of radio sensing technology for the imaging of ground targets include the studies outlined in [2]–[4]. In [2], on the basis of a ray propagation technique, a forward-looking radar imaging algorithm accounting for ground-induced refraction and dispersion is presented for the detection of subsurface targets. In [3], a finite-difference time-domain (FDTD)-based full-wave approach is described for simulating the operation of a ground-penetrating radar system. The two studies above assume the ground interface to be perfectly smooth, whereas the investigation carried out in [4] allows the interface to be rough and characterizes the composite backscattering from the targets and the ground utilizing a heuristic physical optics approach. The scattering effects of the rough ground surface are included in [4] by modeling the roughness in the signal domain as a random phase screen. From the RF remote sensing perspective, the analysis of electromagnetic scattering from random terrain surfaces is in itself a well-known and important problem. Unfortunately, commonly-employed analytical approaches are only useful for limited classes of terrain surfaces and observation geometries encountered in practical forward-looking radar sensing. Given the lack of empirical data and the deficiencies in existing analytical treatments, numerical simulations of surface scattering based on FDTD have been explored in a companion study by the authors. By comparing FDTD-simulated backscattering results to those from a surface integral equation solver, it is shown in [5] that the specific FDTD technique followed therein is an accurate approach for characterizing the surface radio response at low-grazing angles. In view of the developments detailed in [5], a complementary study is carried out in this work to emulate the imaging of targets embedded in a rough ground environment—by using the Message-Passing Interface (MPI)-based 3D-FDTD algorithm featured in [5] as the primary simulation engine for computing wave scattering. The components of

Fig. 1. Forward-looking radar sensing of a terrain scene.

the emulation framework are described in Section II, and the simulated imaging results are presented in Section III.

II. EMULATION FRAMEWORK

In demonstrating the modeling framework put forth in this study, the electromagnetic simulation and coherent imaging of the scene depicted in Fig. 1 is considered.

A. Terrain Characterization

The ground is modeled as a non-dispersive, non-permeable homogeneous medium with effective relative dielectric constant ϵ_r and conductivity σ_d . The electrical properties of the ground are dependent upon the soil composition and moisture content; ϵ_r and σ_d can be either determined using direct dielectric measurement techniques or approximated with empirical-based formulations. The surface statistics of the ground, in general, are described by two functions: the probability density function of the height variations and the surface autocorrelation function. Within the scope of this study, a two-dimensional zero-mean surface profile obeying Gaussian statistics $\{h_{rms}, l_c\}$ —where h_{rms} is the *rms* height and l_c the correlation length—is assumed and generated from its randomized power spectral density function.

B. Ground Targets

As illustrated in Fig. 1, targets in the form of landmines (either anti-tank or anti-personnel, metallic or plastic, buried or on-surface) and 155-*mm* shells (metallic, buried) are considered. Specifically, these targets—the shapes, dimensions, orientations, and locations of which are also indicated by the white outlines in Fig. 2(a)—include the following: 1. Buried metallic anti-personnel landmine; 2. Buried plastic ($\epsilon_r = 3.1$, $\sigma_d = 2 \text{ mS/m}$) anti-personnel landmine; 3. On-surface plastic ($\epsilon_r = 3.1$, $\sigma_d = 2 \text{ mS/m}$) anti-personnel landmine; 4. Buried metallic 155-*mm* shell; 5. Buried metallic anti-tank landmine; 6. On-surface metallic anti-tank landmine; 7. Buried metallic 155-*mm* shell; 8. Buried metallic 155-*mm* shell; 9. On-surface metallic anti-personnel landmine; 10. Buried plastic ($\epsilon_r = 3.1$, $\sigma_d = 2 \text{ mS/m}$) anti-tank landmine; 11. On-surface plastic ($\epsilon_r = 3.1$, $\sigma_d = 2 \text{ mS/m}$) anti-tank landmine. Buried targets are positioned at 3 *cm* below the surface.

C. 3D-FDTD Algorithm

The composite scattering from the targets and the rough ground is calculated numerically with the FDTD method. In the current approach, the targets and a finite-sized rough surface are embedded in an infinite half-space environment.

The solver implements the split field scheme in which the computational domain is partitioned into total and scattered field regions separated by a connective boundary. In the absence of any scatterers (i.e., only the half-space background is present in the scene), the scattered field is null everywhere. A scatterer is defined as any perturbation to the half-space configuration (such as a roughness of the interface, presence of a target, etc.) and generates non-zero scattered field. Note that the incident field is implemented as a plane wave, with the sources at infinity. The incident wavefront is not tapered, but rather a gradual transition from the edges of the rough surface to the infinite flat ground plane is introduced. It is important to emphasize that the above approach is different from those of previous FDTD studies on rough surface scattering in that only the perturbed field due to the interface roughness is calculated here. In fact, the coherent component of the field reflected by the surface is not included in the solution. The advantage of using the outlined FDTD method instead of a surface integral equation routine for simulating grazing-angle interactions has been explained in a companion study [5]. Basically, the surface integral equation routine requires the size of the simulation domain to scale with the reciprocal of $(\sin \theta_{inc})^{1.5}$ because of the inherent need to properly taper the incident wave into a Maxwellian beam; however, the developed FDTD method is not constrained by such a limitation and therefore is expected to be more computationally efficient even for the large-scale simulation domain considered herein.

Throughout this study, the excitation is provided by an unmodulated fourth-order Rayleigh pulse. Yee cells are used to discretize the entire computational volume; as such, the surface interface profile is quantized by a stair-stepped approximation. The MPI-parallelized implementation of the FDTD algorithm from [6] which runs on large distributed computer systems is employed to propagate the radio pulse through the simulation scene. Essentially, the computational domain is decomposed into rectangular sub-domains and the FDTD equations are solved separately for each sub-domain within one MPI process. For further details on the parallel implementation of the algorithm, the reader is referred to [6]. To emulate an infinite propagation domain, the FDTD lattice is surrounded by a perfectly matched layer on all sides. Finally, to compute the far field scattering pattern, a near-to-far zone transformation is performed with the scattered field sampled at points situated immediately outside the connective boundary.

D. Time-Reversal Imaging

A coherent field integration technique is employed to process the FDTD-computed scattered signals to obtain an image of the illuminated scene. According to the time-reversal, or phase-conjugation, method, since the received scattered field can be written as

$$E_s(\vec{r}_R, \vec{r}_T, \omega) = T(\omega) \alpha(\omega) G(\vec{r}_s, \vec{r}_T, \omega) G(\vec{r}_R, \vec{r}_s, \omega), \quad (1)$$

an approximate objective (image) function can be formed with the following expression:

$$O(\vec{r}) = \sum_{\omega} \sum_R \sum_T E_s^*(\vec{r}_R, \vec{r}_T, \omega) G(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_T, \omega) G(\vec{r}_R, \vec{r}, \omega); \quad (2)$$

where the asterisk notation denotes the phase conjugation operation; $G(\vec{r}, \vec{r}', \omega)$ is the Green's function of the environment ($\vec{r}$ is the position of the observation point; $\vec{r}'$ is the position of the source point); $\vec{r}_T$, $\vec{r}_R$, and $\vec{r}_s$ are the locations of the transmitter, receiver, and scatterer, respectively; $T(\omega)$ and $\alpha(\omega)$ are the spectra of the transmitted waveform and target response. The angular and range resolution of the image are determined by the sensor aperture and system bandwidth, respectively, of the coherent summation performed in (2). For sensing in the presence of a randomly-varying ground interface, as the exact propagation Green's function is not known, $G(\vec{r}, \vec{r}', \omega)$ is approximated by the half-space Green's function; as such, the target image is corrupted by ground clutter.

At this point, some important differences between the configuration of the SIRE radar and the setup of the simulation scenario should be mentioned. The SIRE radar transceiver consists of an array of equally-spaced receivers placed across a $2\text{-}m$ aperture and two transmitters situated at the ends of the aperture (Fig.1). The entire assembly is elevated at $2\text{-}m$ height (atop a vehicle) and covers a down-range between 7.5 m and 21 m while the platform is on the move. As the featured FDTD method only implements incidence and scattering in the far-field, plane-wave incidence from two azimuth directions and five elevation angles that span the same solid angle as the SIRE transmitters is considered. For each elevation angle, the scattered fields are computed at equally-spaced azimuth angles (in one-degree increments) that provide similar azimuth coverage as the SIRE receivers. At the limits of the SIRE radar range coverage, the elevation angles and angular apertures correspond to $\theta_{inc} = 5^\circ$, $\Delta\phi = 32^\circ$ and $\theta_{inc} = 15^\circ$, $\Delta\phi = 77^\circ$, respectively, where $\Delta\phi = \phi_2 - \phi_1$. The FDTD simulations were performed at the ARL DoD Supercomputing Resource Center (DSRC) in Aberdeen, MD, on a SGI Altix ICE 8200 system. The discretization of the entire $9\text{ m} \times 19\text{ m} \times 0.5\text{ m}$ scene in Fig. 1 involved 1.7 billion cells (partitioned into 256 sub-domains), and each simulation run at one incidence angle required 256 processors and approximately 2000 CPU hours.

III. RESULTS

The effects of a rough ground surface on focusing are demonstrated with the simulation results displayed in Figs. 2–4, which show the co- and cross-polarization images of the scene considered. As seen in Fig. 2, buried targets are generally more difficult to discern from the background as compared to on-surface targets. For instance, the intensity of the buried metallic anti-tank landmine is about 16 dB below that of the on-surface configuration in vv polarization—for a ground with either a flat or rough surface. The orientation of a target can also have a significant impact on its radar return: maximum response from the 155-mm shell is observed

Fig. 2. Simulated images (vv -polarized) for $9\text{ m} \times 19\text{ m} \times 0.5\text{ m}$ scene in Fig. 1: (a) Ground with flat surface; (b) Ground with randomly rough surface— $h_{rms} = 5\text{ mm}$, $l_c = 7\text{ cm}$; (c) Ground with randomly rough surface— $h_{rms} = 7.5\text{ mm}$, $l_c = 7\text{ cm}$. Ground electrical properties: $\epsilon_r = 8$, $\sigma_d = 10\text{ mS/m}$.

when it is oriented parallel to the imaging aperture; a much weaker response is noted when it is oriented perpendicular or obliquely (at 45°) to the aperture. These observations are consistent with the analysis previously reported. As the scattering from the rough surface is a random process, the coherent correlation operation in (2) is expected to partly suppress the overall response from the ground. However, as evident from Fig. 2(b), with vv polarization, even for $h_{rms} = 5\text{ mm}$, the background clutter can still almost mask the returns from targets such as buried anti-personnel landmines and 155-mm shells. On the other hand, as seen in Figs. 3(b) and 4(b), hh and hv polarizations prove to be slightly more effective in separating certain targets (for example, targets 1 and 8) from the background. Note that the images as presented have been normalized with respect to the maximum intensity found within each image; consequently, the background clutter appears to be more suppressed in the hh - and hv -polarized images due to the relatively stronger response of the on-surface anti-tank landmines at those polarizations. In considering image intensity alone, the differences among the various polarizations in their effectiveness in discriminating targets from the

Fig. 3. Simulated hh -polarized images for same scene as Fig.2.

clutter are less noticeable at the larger surface roughness of $h_{rms} = 7.5 \text{ mm}$ (as compared to the case of $h_{rms} = 5 \text{ mm}$). Nevertheless, it is interesting to note the “butterfly-like” shape generated by each point target in the hv -polarized images; the distinctive signature is due to the azimuthal anti-symmetry in the cross-polarized field pattern radiated by the induced target currents flowing along the excitation wave incidence directions. It should be asserted that—within the context of the present work—this phenomenon is only observable for certain radar imaging configurations: for example, it is not visible in the strictly monostatic-based sensing scenario or for $\theta_{inc} = 0^\circ$.

IV. CONCLUSION

In view of the inadequacies of standard analytical approaches for characterizing grazing-angle scattering mechanisms and interactions, the utility of a full-wave electromagnetic solver in supporting performance prediction for standoff radio sensing applications is investigated. The implemented emulation methodology employs a MPI-parallelized three-dimensional FDTD algorithm in modeling the composite scattering from targets and the ground. The effects of surface clutter on time-reversal-based target imaging are illustrated with the simulation of a large realistic scene consisting of landmines

Fig. 4. Simulated hv -polarized images for same scene as Fig.2.

and 155- mm shells embedded in a ground environment exhibiting a randomly-varying interface. Collectively, the results and observations featured in this study represent the first step taken in understanding and predicting the fundamental impact of ground surface clutter on the performance of the forward-looking radar for in-road and roadside target detection. Future work will strive to include more realistic features of the SIRE radar imaging geometry as well as the terrain scene.

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